

NON-CRIMP 3D WEAVE vs. LAMINATED PLANE WEAVE COMPOSITES: TENSION-TENSION FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR

V. Carvelli¹, G. Gramellini¹, S.V. Lomov², A.E. Bogdanovich³, D.D. Mungalov³,
I. Verpoest²

¹ Department of Structural Engineering, Politecnico di Milano
Piazza Leonardo Da Vinci 32, 20133, Milan, Italy

² Department MTM, K.U. Leuven
Kasteelpark Arenberg, 44, B-3001, Leuven, Belgium

³ 3TEX Inc., 109 MacKenan Drive, Cary, NC 27511, USA

ABSTRACT

This paper presents results of a comparative experimental study of the tensile-tensile fatigue behavior of composite materials reinforced with non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven and equivalent thickness laminated 2D plane woven E-glass fabrics. The failure-free thresholds and Wöhler (S-N) curves of the two materials are obtained and compared. The damage imparted during tension-tension fatigue tests is investigated by a combination of mechanical testing, acoustic emission registration (AE), progressive cracks observation on transparent samples and full-field surface strain mapping.

Keywords: Textile Composite, Non-crimp 3D woven, 2D plain weave, Fatigue, Damage.

INTRODUCTION

Relatively thick, single layer non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven preforms are gaining fast growing interest in the composites industry. Composites reinforced with single-layer non-crimp 3D woven preforms are nowadays used in a broad range of applications: from personnel and ground vehicle composite armor, to load bearing structures such as bridge decks or windmill blades, marine structures like boats and yachts, and aircraft engines [1].

Efficient modern methods of low-cost manufacturing of non-crimp 3D single-layer preforms increased the interest in the research activities to exploit the full potentialities of these materials. The research and experimental activities allowed to well understand and to appreciate that 3D woven non-crimp reinforcement provides efficient delamination suppression, markedly improves fracture toughness [2], significantly increases damage tolerance as well as impact, ballistic and blast performances [3-5], and also provides relatively high in-plane strength properties compared to 2D fabric laminates [6]. The latter is caused, primarily, by the absence of crimp in the inner warp and fill yarn layers, with only minimal crimp observed in the surface fill yarn layers due

to their interaction with through thickness (Z) yarns. The absence of other types of fiber waviness and misalignment is due to the specialty 3D orthogonal weaving process and machines, see further information in [7, 8].

One primarily important issue in several industrial applications is the fatigue behavior of non-crimp 3D woven composites. Fatigue data for these composites are on a high demand by industry. At the same time, this topic has been barely touched for the 3D interlock weave composites [9] and, to the best of these authors' knowledge, no data of this kind are available in literature for non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave composites.

A recent comprehensive experimental study on the static tensile behavior of non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave composites [10, 11] suggests their higher in-plane damage initiation thresholds, ultimate stress and strain characteristics in comparison with those of the equivalent thickness plain weave laminates. Do those results allow one to expect a better fatigue performance of non-crimp 3D woven composites vs. their plain weave laminated equivalent? A tentative answer is given in this paper, which presents first comparative experimental study of the tension-tension fatigue behavior of one typical non-crimp 3D weave E-glass composite and the equivalent plain weave laminate.

Specifically, the materials considered and compared in this study are (i) composite reinforced with a single-ply non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave E-glass fabric (the fabric fragment is shown in Figure 1a) and (ii) laminated composite reinforced with four plies of plain weave E-glass fabric (a fragment of plain weave is shown in Figure 1b). Details of these materials can be found in the next section and a complete description in [10].

The aims of this study are to: (i) generate and compare the Wöhler (S-N) curves for both composite materials, (ii) deduce the “infinite fatigue life” load; (iii) evaluate residual fatigue strength and stiffness degradation by means of the post-fatigue traction tests on the samples undergone five million cycles at “infinite life” stress level.

Figure 1. Internal architecture of: (a) non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave single-ply preform; (b) 2D plain weave fabric.

EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS

Two types of composites reinforced with E-glass fabric preforms were produced by VARTM method for this study by 3TEX, Inc. using Dow Derakane 8084 Epoxy-Vinyl Ester resin. A non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave single-ply preform (3255 g/m^2 areal density) and a four-ply symmetric stack $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ of plain weave fabric (total areal

density 3260 g/m²) were used to manufacture the two types of composite, which are termed in the rest of the paper as “3D” and “2D”, respectively.

3D single-ply orthogonal weave preform was produced by 3TEX, Inc. The weave is made of PPG Hybon 2022 E-glass roving in warp, fill and Z directions; the fiber architecture is formed by 3 warp and 4 fill (a.k.a. “weft”) layers. The middle warp layer uses 450 yield (1100 tex) roving, while the other two warp layers, placed symmetrically with respect to the mid-surface, use 218 yield (2275 tex) roving; all layers have 2.76 ends/cm insertion density. All fill layers use 330 yield (1470 tex) roving with 2.64 picks/cm insertion density. Warp and fill layers are interlaced by through thickness Z roving, inserted by two harnesses with 2.76 ends/cm insertion; Z-directional reinforcement uses 1800 yield (276 tex) roving. This fabric construction results in ~49% warp, ~49% fill and ~2% Z fiber content per preform volume.

The plain weave is made of 2275 tex PPG Hybon 2022 E-glass roving, used both in warp and weft directions; the respective insertion densities are 1.95 ends/cm in warp and 1.60 picks/cm in weft directions. Resulting from this, the fabric is slightly unbalanced with respect to the total fiber volume content in the warp and weft directions. In order to reach the overall fiber balance in composite laminate, the fabric layer orientation was alternated, like 0/90/90/0°, when laying the four-ply preform. Due to the balanced warp- and weft-directional fiber content, fatigue characterization of the 2D composite has been performed in warp direction only.

The composite panels of this kind were earlier used in a comprehensive experimental study of the in-plane static tensile properties of the two composite materials [10, 11]. The obtained static damage initiation thresholds and the ultimate stress and strain values were applied in the present study for determining the consecutive stress levels of fatigue loading. In the following section the summary on the static tensile test results is presented for the materials to be studied here.

BASELINE STATIC TEST DATA

Table 1 shows the mean stiffness and strength properties of the two materials in terms of: Young’s modulus (E) in the two fiber directions (warp and fill); in-plane Poisson’s ratio (ν); ultimate stress (σ_{ult}) and ultimate strain (ϵ_{ult}). The mean stress-strain curves shown in Figure 2a reveal very small difference between the stiffness of the two materials (see Table 1). The difference is mainly attributed to the slightly higher total fiber volume fraction (V_f) in the 2D composite, 52.4% vs. 48.9% in 3D. After scaling to the equal total fiber volume fraction, the difference in Young’s moduli disappears. The static tensile tests showed significantly higher ultimate stress and strain values for the 3D as compared to the 2D composite, see Table 1.

The damage initiation thresholds were determined in [10] by an acoustic emission system. Two AE sensors were situated at the boundaries of the gauge length region. During the test a change in the rate of AE event accumulation indicates a switch to another damage mechanism. Figure 2b shows typical results of AE registration. The processing of these results allowed to determine: the AE Threshold Strain (AETS) ϵ_{min} , for which relatively low energy acoustic events start to occur; the First Damage Threshold Strain (FDTS) ϵ_1 at the first increase of the slope of the cumulative AE energy curve; the Second Damage Threshold Strain (SDTS) ϵ_2 at the second “knee” on

the AE cumulative energy curve. The mean values of the AETS, FDTS and SDTS levels are given in Table 1. The main conclusion made in [10] from the static tensile property study was that the non-crimp 3D woven composite has significantly higher damage initiation thresholds and ultimate strains and stresses in both fill and warp directions than its laminated plain weave counterpart.

Type, V_f %	Direction	E , GPa	$E@50\%$ V_f	ν	σ_{ult} , MPa	σ_{ult} @50% V_f	ϵ_{ult} , %	ϵ_{min} , %	ϵ_1 , %	ϵ_2 , %
3D	Warp	24.3±1.2	24.6±1.2	0.143±0.159	429±34	435±34	2.74±0.29	0.26±0.11	0.43±0.04	0.54±0.04
48.9	Fill	25.1±2.3	25.5±2.3	0.128±0.081	486±5	493±5	3.33±0.27	0.16±0.05	0.37±0.06	0.59±0.04
2D	Warp/ Weft	26.0±1.5	24.8±1.5	0.207±0.091	413±4	394±4	2.38±0.02	0.15±0.04	0.26±0.04	0.43±0.06

Table 1. Experimental in-plane static properties of the 3D and 2D composites [10].

Figure 2. (a) Tensile diagrams and (b) acoustic emission registration from the static tests in warp and fill directions of 3D vs. 2D woven composites [10].

TENSION-TENSION FATIGUE TESTS

The response to fatigue loading of the composite materials was investigated by tension-tension cyclic tests. The samples were extracted from panels of non-crimp 3D composite in warp and fill direction and of 2D plain weave laminate in warp direction of the outer layers. The measured mean fiber volume fraction of the panels used in the fatigue characterization was 50.6% for 3D and 51.6% for 2D. The samples had prismatic shape 250mm overall length, 25mm width and ~2.5mm thickness. Aluminum tabs, 50mm long and 2mm thick, were used to grip the sample in a MTS testing machine. The tests were performed under constant stress amplitude, sinusoidal tensile loading and assuming the ratio $R = 0.1$ (ratio of the minimum to the maximum stress in the cycle). The frequency was set in the range 2÷10Hz depending on the stress level.

Different maximum stress levels were considered in the experimental characterization; from a level 300MPa, which is close to the static ultimate stress, to the level of 60-65 MPa, which did not lead to failure after 5 million cycles. The latter one can be used as

the “infinite fatigue life” characteristic, i.e. the level at which damage (if it is originated) does not progress, and the specimen does not ultimately fail.

To avoid the influence of the tabs zones and the grips pressure, a cyclic test was considered “valid” if the sample broke at a distance greater than 2cm from the tabs. At least three valid samples were tested for each stress level.

Figure 3. Non-crimp 3D woven composite loading in (a) warp and (b) fill direction.

Figure 4. Damage in the non-crimp 3D woven composite after fatigue test: (a) max load 65 MPa in warp, no failure after 5 mln cycles; (b) max load 70 MPa in fill direction, failure after 2.25 mln cycles.

A typical result of the tension-tension fatigue tests is summarized in Figure 3 for the samples of non-crimp 3D composite. The stress vs. displacement cycles in Figure 3a show the behavior of the material loaded in warp direction at the “infinite life” stress level (65MPa). At this stress level, static tests showed certain initial damage in the material, but that remained stable and did not progress, as shown by the invariance of the slope and of the shape of the cycles between 1 million and 5 million cycles. This damage is clearly seen in the bright transmitting light, owing to sufficient transparency of the glass/epoxy composite. Figure 4a shows diffuse, stable transversal cracks in the matrix initiated in the resin pockets extended from the intersections of fill-directional and Z-directional rovings. The same damage pattern was observed in the static tests [11]

at the early stage of loading close to 0.3% longitudinal strain. Lengths of the cracks, detected during the static tests, were close to the width of the Z yarn. The fatigue loading increases the length of these cracks up to a stable size, which is close to the width of the warp yarns (see Figure 4a).

Contrary to that, a stress level higher than the “infinite life” level generates progressively increasing damage, which ultimately results in a total failure of the sample under cyclic loading. This behavior is reproduced in Figure 3b for a 3D sample loaded in fill direction; the slope and the area of the cycles increase with the growing number of cycles up to the complete failure of the sample. During the cyclic fill-loading, besides the initial diffused transverse cracks parallel to the warp direction, some cracks also appear in fill direction; they are situated near the crossover points between the fill and Z yarns (see Figure 4b). These cracks lead to the failure (as was also observed in [11]).

Having results for the two materials response to cyclic tensile loading at different stress levels allowed us to construct the Wöhler-like curves in Figure 5 and Figure 6 for non-crimp 3D and plain weave 2D composites, respectively. In these plots the experimental data are fitted by spline curves (solid lines). Figure 5 and Figure 6 combine the results of three batches of production of composite panels made by 3TEX within 6 months period. The difference in behaviour of 2D composites and 3D composites tested in warp and weft directions is demonstrated by the data in Figure 7, which compares the data for the samples from the same production batch.

The fatigue performance of the non-crimp 3D composite in the principal (warp and fill) directions is found in exact correspondence with the trends observed earlier in the static tests [10]. It is better in fill (Figure 5b) than in warp (Figure 5a) direction, except for stress levels close to the “infinite life” level ($\approx 65\text{MPa}$), where the fatigue performance of the 3D composite is similar in both directions. For each stress level above 100MPa, the fill-directional loading results in ultimate failure at the number of cycles at least 34% higher than that in the case of warp-directional loading, see Figure 7.

Figure 5. Non-crimp 3D woven composite, fatigue life curve in (a) warp and (b) fill loading direction.

Figure 6. Fatigue life curve of the 2D plain weave composite.

Figure 7 Comparison of the fatigue life at different stress levels for the 3D and 2D composites. Vertical lines indicate average fatigue life. All samples from the same production batch.

The 2D composite has a fatigue life curve similar to the non-crimp 3D material in warp direction. The 2D composite gives the numbers of cycles to failure between 8 and 15% higher than the 3D composite tested in warp direction for stress levels above 100MPa, see Figure 7. Close “infinite life” stress levels have been determined for the 2D composite and the 3D composite tested in warp direction. The 2D composite shows

significantly worse fatigue performance than the 3D composite tested in fill direction, except for the stress levels close to the “infinite life”. For the stress levels above 100MPa the fill-directional loading of the 3D composite results in ultimate failure at the numbers of cycles which are 15÷37% higher than those for the 2D composite, see Figure 7.

POST-FATIGUE ANALYSES

The residual fatigue strength and stiffness of the two composites were evaluated by means of post-fatigue traction tests on the samples undergone a cyclic loading at the “infinite fatigue life” stress level (that was determined under condition that ultimate failure did not occur before 5 million cycles).

In Figure 8 the comparison between the stress vs. strain diagrams of 3D samples, loaded in warp direction, shows the degradation effect of the cyclic loading at 65MPa (“infinite fatigue life” stress level). The stiffness of the fatigue damaged material (post-fatigue stiffness) did not have a significant variation with respect to the stiffness of undamaged material (pre-fatigue stiffness). The damage introduced during the cyclic test provides 20% lower residual failure stress than the ultimate failure stress in Table 1.

The post-fatigue study included static tensile testing with Acoustic Emission registration by the same system (AMSY-5, Vallen System GmbH) as employed in the static study of the same composites [10, 11] and in other experimental studies [12]. Two typical AE diagrams are shown in Figure 9 for the 3D and 2D samples previously fatigued in warp direction under 5 million cycles. In the beginning of the tests, the frequency of AE events is negligible. With the load increase the number of recorded events drastically increases at about the same stress level as imposed during the fatigue test (65MPa). This observation shows that the amount of damage introduced during the cyclic test (transversal cracks in the yarns and matrix) remains almost constant with the static load below the infinite fatigue stress level. When increasing the static load above this limit, the density of the transversal cracks drastically grows, and further damage develops, i.e. the cracks in longitudinal direction continue growing up to the ultimate failure.

Figure 8. Non-crimp 3D composite: comparison of pre- and post-fatigue static tensile tests in warp direction.

Figure 9. Typical AE diagrams for post-fatigue static tensile tests: 3D in warp direction (left) and 2D (right).

CONCLUSIONS

The comparative experimental study presented in this paper deals with tensile-tensile fatigue behavior of composite materials reinforced with non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven and equivalent thickness laminated 2D plane woven E-glass fabrics. The damage-free thresholds and Wöhler (S-N) curves of the two materials allow the following preliminary conclusion: the 3D composite tested in warp direction shows the lowest number of cycles to failure; the 2D composite shows considerably higher number of cycles to failure than the 3D composite tested in warp direction, but significantly lower number of cycles to failure than the same 3D composite tested in fill direction. A mechanistic reason for these effects has not been found yet.

At all stress levels the fatigue life of the studied non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven composite is much longer under fill-directional than under warp-directional loading with the same tensile stress amplitude. This is very important practical conclusion, asking to reconsider the established 3D fabric design concept, where the fabric architectures were required to be balanced with respect to the total amount of fibers in the warp and fill directions. In the fatigue-sensitive design cases the warp direction has to be enhanced with additional fibers, in order to reduce respective maximum of in-service stress and ensure equal fatigue life for the warp and fill directions.

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